

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This demonstrator allows to proof the possibility of establishing a lean production for an individualized serial product transferring the spirit of the platform technology created and established in the car building industry. Furthermore, the fully digitalized configuration based on a matrix and creating a one stop shop from the perspective of the clients is representing an essential part of the tiny house demonstrator.

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

- › Master Thesis written by Francisco Alejandro López Ramírez: Optimization of Circular Tiny House Construction: Applying 2D Bin Packing and Generative Design in BIM
- › https://tubcloud.tuberlin.de/apps/files/files/4114381342?dir=/Groupfolder/civilsystems_member_gf/Projects/REINCARNATE/TUBStudies&editing=false&openfile=true

Location

Berlin, Germany

Innovation

The targeted user group are people interested in tiny house offers. These SIG will also be more willing to adopt reused materials and building products. Therefore, in this demonstration it will promote the possibility to entirely built tiny houses from reused materials and products. To this end, around all materials and products of all REINCARNATE demonstration projects, project partner 3L will support the development of a parametric BIM-based design tool for tiny houses making use of existing reused products and recycle materials at a specific time. Additionally, possibilities for robotic automation for assembling tiny houses have been explored using TUB robot cell. At project´s end, a tiny house completely built from reused components and recycled materials was foreseen to be built and show cased in Berlin. The total costs of this realisation including a robot application, DFRA and material storage have been investigated and proved by market partner offers. The total amount exceeded the available budget for demonstrators and the Technical Board decided to switch the nature to virtual.

Partners

3L, TUB

IMPACT

HIGH

Techno-Economic
Impact

HIGH

Societal Impact

HIGH

Scientific Impact

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

KPIs are following all building codes of the German market. Furthermore, the integration of reused building materials is integrated into this technical approach.

IMAGES

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